

INCIDENCE OF MAJOR PESTS IN BAEI, *AEGLE MARMELLOS* AS INFLUENCED BY
ABIOTIC FACTORS IN ARID REGION OF RAJASTHAN

V. Karuppaiah, S. L. Jat, S. K. Sharma and R. S. Singh

Central Institute for Arid Horticulture, Bikaner, Rajasthan-334006

Email: haldhar80@gmail.com

The Bael, *Aegle marmelos* is gaining popularity among the farmers of arid and semi arid areas for economic cultivation. However, the quality of fruits and productivity is not obtained up to the standard. One of the reasons for it is infestation of insect pests on the vegetative as well as developing fruits which ultimately leads to significant yield loss and quality attributes of the fruits. Looking in to the severity of insect pest infestation, we have conducted study throughout the year at Experimental Farm, Central Institute for Arid Horticulture during 2008-2010. It revealed from the study that the damaging effect of swallow tail butterfly *Papilio demoleus* was recorded on bael from September to February. The damaging intensity of this butterfly was recorded 45 to 50 percent leaves damage. The peak population (egg and larvae) of butterfly was observed in November (12.3 eggs & 6.1 larvae/ 10 branches). The relationship between swallow tail butterfly infestation and temperature was negatively correlated whereas the relative humidity was positively correlated. Beside this, the fruit fly, *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) was found to damage severely to fruits of bael during 2009-10 in all important cultivars growing in the farm. The infested fruits drop-off before to mature. The fruit cracking and rotting also observed in the infested fruits. About 40 to 50 larva has been observed from the single fruit. The active maggot comes out from the dropped fruit through split puncture after the crack for pupation. The infestation (fruit drop) was noticed in the cultivars such as NB 5, NB 7, NB 9, Pant Aparna, Pant Urvashi, Pant Shivani, Pant Sujatha. The more fruit drop was noticed in the late season cultivars.

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“EFFECT OF AUXIN AND ROOTING MEDIA ON MULTIPLICATION OF APPLE
CLONAL ROOTSTOCK (MERTON 793)”

P. C. Khatik, D. D. Sharma, K. Dev and Karan

Department of Fruit Science, Dr Y S Parmar University of Horticulture and Forestry,
Nauni, Solan (H P)-173230

Corresponding author's E Mail prakashkhatik@ymail.com

The investigations were carried out at the nursery area of Department of Fruit Science, Dr Y S Parmar University of Horticulture and Forestry, Nauni, Solan during 2009-2010. The study consisted of two experiments, which were laid out in the randomized block design. In the first experiment, different concentrations of IBA and NAA viz. (i) 1500 ppm IBA; (ii) 2000 ppm IBA; (iii) 2500 ppm IBA; (iv) 3000 ppm NAA; (v) 4000 ppm NAA; (vi) 5000 ppm NAA; (vii) 1500 ppm IBA + 3000 ppm NAA and control. The results revealed that highest percentage of rooted stool shoot (84.57 %), number of rooted stool shoots (7.23/stool), number of adventitious roots per stool shoot (17.71), total root length (4.80 m), linear growth of stool shoot (127.76 cm), stool shoot diameter (12.03 mm), leaf area (11.31 cm²), root to shoot ratio (0.088), and total biomass in terms of fresh (110.38 g) and dry weight (67.08 g) was recorded in the stool shoots treated with IBA 2500 ppm. Whereas, the number of leaves per stool shoot (78.99) and average root diameter (1.64 mm) was recorded in IBA 1500 ppm + NAA 3000 ppm treatments. In the